

Ontological Theory behind Interacting Scalar Quantum Field Theory

M.Th.M. van Kessel¹

March 20, 2026

Abstract

We show how one can reproduce the state evolution known from *interacting* QFT from an ontological deterministic theory. This is an important step in finding the reality that underlies QFT.

In previous work ontic theories behind *free* QFTs were found, for all QFTs that occur in the Standard Model (spin-0, spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ & spin-1). In this paper we extend the ontological theory behind QFT to the case *with* interactions. We do this by starting out from the ontic theories found for free QFTs and see what happens if we try to include interactions (known from QFT). This will lead us to the conjecture that the ontic theory behind any QFT with interaction is, at the basis, the corresponding classical field theory. We study such a classical field theory for the case of a real scalar field with φ^n -interaction. We determine the evolution of the probability density of the ontic fields and cast it into a formalism known from QFT. We will focus on the simplest case of self-interaction, to illustrate our procedure. We find that we can reproduce the probability evolution from real scalar QFT with (self-)interaction, for this simplest case.

¹MThMvanKessel@gmail.com

1 Introduction

Since the birth of Quantum Mechanics (QM), and later Quantum Field Theory (QFT), physicists have asked themselves what is actually happening in any experiment at the quantum level. What is the reality behind our macroscopic observations, and what is happening at each step in time in the course of a QM experiment?

A key example here is the two-slit experiment. In this experiment a particle, let's say an electron, is emitted from a source and directed towards a thin wall with two slits. At some distance behind the wall is placed a detection screen, on which, in case the electron passes the thin wall, the electron shows up as a dot, i.e. as a point particle. We want to know what is actually happening in this experiment, from the moment the electron leaves the source, moves towards the thin wall, passes the thin wall (going through one of the two slits?), moves towards the detection screen, and is finally detected. How should we visualize this process in our mind? Is the electron a point particle, is it a wave, or is it something else? In other words we want to know the ontology of the experiment being performed. To really understand the experiment, we need to have a picture in our mind that corresponds 1-to-1 to what is happening in reality.

In QM, and in QFT, questions of this type are not answered and dismissed as unimportant and metaphysical. It is stated that the theory should only answer questions directly related to observations, the rest being speculation. Here the author of this paper strongly disagrees. Physics became a successful science not by dodging questions, not wondering what is behind certain observations, but by asking further and further. One only understands something if one can make a picture in ones mind, that corresponds 1-to-1 to reality. If certain parts of this picture are blurry, then one doesn't understand yet. In the above case of the two-slit experiment we have no consistent picture yet of the electron from when it leaves the source to when it hits the detection screen. One cannot visualize the electron to be a point particle, with local interactions, since then one would not get an interference pattern. One can also not visualize the electron as a wave, since then one doesn't get a single dot detected on the screen. So what is it then?

This is exactly the question the author has been asking himself. And this is why we say we are searching for an ontological theory behind QFT. We are satisfied when, in the case of the two-slit experiment, we have a clear picture in mind of what the electron actually is, for all time-steps from source to detection screen. In this sense we agree with other authors who have been researching the same question, most notably [2].

A first step one can make to get to such an understanding of reality is to find ontological states in QFT. This is the strategy followed in [2], [3], [4], [10], [11] & [12]. By ontological states, or ontic states for short, we mean states in the QFT state space that

- evolve in time into each other,
- span the full QFT state space,
- are orthogonal.

For a more elaborate explanation see [1] and [2]. The variables parametrizing these states could then be regarded as the objects of reality, because these variables follow a specific (deterministic) evolution law, and we know what is going on (i.e. the values of these variables) at each step in time. Any superposition of ontic states is interpreted as a situation where there is uncertainty about the values these variables have. The idea of these ontic states is extensively discussed in literature, see [2].

In a previous paper [1] the author summarized the ontological states currently known for all free QFTs that occur in the Standard Model. For each type of QFT (scalar QFT, Dirac QFT, spin-1 QFT) a set of ontic states for the case of no interaction is known. A logical next step is to find the ontic states for QFTs *with* interaction. This is what this paper is about.

Several general steps towards this were taken already in [10], [11], [12] & [13]. There one is still quite far from the interactions known from QFTs and in the SM. In this paper we want to focus on the interactions that do occur in the SM and in reality.

In this paper we will focus on real scalar QFT, with φ^n -interactions.

1.1 Outline

Our starting point will be the ontic theory found behind free scalar QFT, in [3], [4] and summarized in [1]. In section 2 we will give a short recap of this.

In section 3 we will see how we can add interaction to the ontic theory for free scalar QFT. We will see that, to add interaction in a local way, we need the introduction of a new ontic variable $\rho(\vec{k})$, next to the ontic variable $\varphi(\vec{k})$ known from the free theory. Having added this new ontic variable, the ontic theory has become a classical free field theory for a scalar field. For such a classical field theory it is easy to add interactions in a local and relativistic way. We will discuss the relation between the ontic states found here and the ones found earlier in [3] and [1].

In section 4 we will determine what the interaction from QFT would mean for the evolution of the ontic states known from free QFT, and for the evolution of the corresponding ontic variables. We do this for the case of scalar QFT with φ^3 -interaction. There it will become clear that the QFT evolution results in a non-deterministic evolution for the ontic variables known from the free theory. The new ontic variables $\rho(\vec{k})$ found in section 3 will help explain this.

In section 5 we will add interaction to our ontic theory. We will do this for φ^3 -interaction. Given that we eventually want to reproduce QFT with interaction we study the evolution of the probability over the classical fields. We find that the evolution of the probability density in terms of the ontic fields $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k})$ (and not e.g. the one terms of the ontic fields $\varphi(\vec{x})$ and $\dot{\varphi}(\vec{x})$) closely resembles the one from QFT. We will derive the evolution law for this probability, and cast it into a form known from QFT. We will find that this evolution, from the purely classical field theory, is very similar to the QFT evolution.

In section 6 we will investigate the similar, but much simpler case of φ^1 -interaction. Also here we will determine the (purely classical) evolution of the probability density. We will cast it into a form similar to QFT, using states from a Hilbert space. We show that, for certain sets of states from this space, one reproduces an evolution very similar to the one from QFT. We believe that, by tuning this set of states, we will be able to exactly reproduce the probability evolution in *interacting* QFT.

This is a very surprising and important result. The author at first believed that to reproduce QFT evolution with a classical deterministic theory we should at least add some special ingredient, like e.g. the fast variables proposed in [10]. It turns out however that selecting a limited set of states in our ontic theory is enough. (The author still believes that, to show that states outside this limited set do not occur in reality, and in QFT, we might need such a special ingredient like fast variables.)

In section 7 we will summarize our main finding, and discuss important open questions.

In section 8 we will discuss why the author prefers to look for an ontological explanation of QFT among continuous classical field theories, instead of among cellular automata, as other theorists have proposed [2].

2 Ontic Theory behind Free Scalar QFT

In this section we will recap the ontic states found for free real scalar QFT in [3], [4] and summarized in [1].

2.1 Recap

The ontic states will be formulated in terms of the annihilation and creation operators a and a^\dagger from real scalar QFT. These operators satisfy the wellknown commutation relations

$$\begin{aligned} [a(\vec{k}), a^\dagger(\vec{l})] &= (2\pi)^3 \omega_k \delta^3(\vec{k} - \vec{l}) \\ [a(\vec{k}), a(\vec{l})] &= 0 \\ [a^\dagger(\vec{k}), a^\dagger(\vec{l})] &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

with $\omega_k \equiv c\sqrt{\vec{k}^2 + \mu^2}$, $\mu \equiv (mc)/\hbar$ and m the mass of the scalar particle. With the creation operators we can build a set of basis states for the QFT Hilbert space. These basis states are

$$a^\dagger(\vec{k}_1) \dots a^\dagger(\vec{k}_n) |0\rangle, \tag{2}$$

where $|0\rangle$ is the vacuum state of the free QFT.

To formulate the ontic states we discretize momentum space on a lattice with spacing Δk and enumerate the vectors \vec{k} with a discrete index i .

The ontic states for real free scalar (spin-0) QFT are:

$$|\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots\rangle_{\text{ont}} = \prod_i \left[\sum_{n_i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n_i!}} \left(\frac{\Delta k^{3/2}}{(2\pi)^{3/2} \sqrt{c\sqrt{\vec{k}_i^2 + \mu^2}}} \right)^{n_i} e^{-i\varphi_i n_i} \left(a^\dagger(\vec{k}_i) \right)^{n_i} \right] |0\rangle \tag{3}$$

Here the product over i is a product over all discrete values of \vec{k} , i.e. all \vec{k}_i 's. These ontic states are the same ones as found in [3] & [4].

We can also write the expression for these states in a shorter way:

$$|\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots\rangle_{\text{ont}} \equiv |\varphi(\vec{k})\rangle_{\text{ont}} \tag{4}$$

Each ontic state is defined by the values φ_{i_2} which can each take on the values in $[0, 2\pi)$, and there is one such value φ_i for each \vec{k}_i . In [3] these values are interpreted as cogwheel positions and there are as many cogwheels as there are momentum values \vec{k}_i .

Having found these ontic states we can say that the reality behind free scalar QFT is a set of cogwheels, one for each momentum value \vec{k}_i , each with cogwheel position φ_i . These cogwheel positions evolve in time as:

$$\varphi_i(t) = \varphi_i(t=0) + c\sqrt{\vec{k}_i^2 + \mu^2} t \pmod{2\pi} \tag{5}$$

In our ontic theory we can now build states, called template states in [2], which are superpositions of the ontic states:

$$|\psi\rangle = \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_1 \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_2 \dots c(\varphi(\vec{k})) |\varphi(\vec{k})\rangle_{\text{ont}} \quad (6)$$

We interpret these states as corresponding to a situation where one is uncertain about the actual values of the cogwheel positions φ_i . The complex coefficients c in these template states are related to the probability density P , to find our system of cogwheels in exactly the situation with values $\varphi(\vec{k})$, as

$$P(\varphi(\vec{k})) = |c(\varphi(\vec{k}))|^2. \quad (7)$$

This is the Born rule in QM. It is very convenient, although not absolutely necessary, to work with complex coefficients related to the probabilities as above. See appendix 1 for an explanation of this.

The states (3) are the eigenstates of the beables found in [3] and are the ontic states for a harmonic oscillator, in the continuum limit. The beables are exactly the operators b from [3]. This we can show as follows.

The beables belonging to the ontic states (3) are

$$\varphi_{\text{op}}(\vec{k}_i) = \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_1 \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_2 \dots \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_{i-1} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_i e^{-i\varphi_i} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_{i+1} \dots |\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots\rangle_{\text{ont}} \langle \varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots|. \quad (8)$$

Here in principal the eigenvalue $e^{i\varphi_i}$ can be chosen anyway one likes, here we chose it such as to get exactly to the operators b in [3], eq. (4.8).

Now by plugging in the ontic states in terms of the a^\dagger 's (3) and performing the integrals over the φ 's one can show that this becomes

$$\varphi_{\text{op}}(\vec{k}_i) = \left(I + \alpha^2 a^\dagger(\vec{k}_i) a(\vec{k}_i) \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \alpha a(\vec{k}_i), \quad (9)$$

with

$$\alpha = \frac{\Delta k^{3/2}}{(2\pi)^{3/2} \sqrt{c \sqrt{k_i^2 + \mu^2}}}, \quad (10)$$

which are the beables b found in [3], eq. (4.8) (apart from the factor α). By choosing $e^{+i\varphi_i}$ in (8) we would get the other beables b^\dagger from [3]:

$$\varphi_{\text{op}}^\dagger(\vec{k}_i) = \alpha a^\dagger(\vec{k}_i) \left(I + \alpha^2 a^\dagger(\vec{k}_i) a(\vec{k}_i) \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (11)$$

The factor α arises because we expressed the ontic states in terms of the continuum annihilation and creation operators, while in [3] the beables are expressed in terms of the discrete annihilation and creation operators, which satisfy $[a, a^\dagger] = 1$.

Note that one can also find how the creation- and annihilation-operators work on any ontic state. This we will need below in section 4. For one momentum mode \vec{k} the a^\dagger and a work as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} a^\dagger &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sqrt{k} |k\rangle \langle k-1| \\ a &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sqrt{k} |k-1\rangle \langle k| \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Including that for other momentum modes these operators work as unity, including all the continuum constants, and expressing the energy states $|k\rangle$ in terms of the ontic states we find the full expression:

$$a(\vec{k}_i) = \left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta k}\right)^{3/2} \left(c^2 \vec{k}^2 + c^2 \mu^2\right)^{1/4} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi'_1 \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi'_2 \dots \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_i \left(\sum_{k_i=0}^{\infty} \sqrt{k_i} e^{i+(k_i-1)\varphi_i - k_i\varphi'_i}\right) |\varphi'_1, \varphi'_2, \dots, \varphi'_{i-1}, \varphi_i, \varphi'_{i+1}, \dots\rangle_{\text{ont}} \langle \varphi'_1, \varphi'_2, \dots| \quad (13)$$

The operator a^\dagger of course works as the Hermitean conjugate of this.

2.2 Note on Discrete vs. Continuous Cogwheels

An important note to the above is that actually the construction of ontic states (3) only works when we allow the sums over the n_i 's to go only up to a large but finite N . The observant reader probably already noticed that when proving orthogonality of the ontic states in [1] we used

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} e^{ik\varphi} = 2\pi \delta(\varphi \bmod 2\pi). \quad (14)$$

However this is not correct, in the continuum the correct expression is

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{ik\varphi} = 2\pi \delta(\varphi \bmod 2\pi). \quad (15)$$

Only in the discrete situation we can say

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^N e^{ik2\pi j/N} = \delta_{j,0 \bmod N}. \quad (16)$$

And only for the discrete case we can therefore prove the ontic states (3) to be truly a set of ontic states. This is also why in [2] and [3] only discrete ontic theories behind free scalar QFT are discussed. Only for discrete cogwheels, with also a discrete time (as dictated of course by the evolution law (5)), does the mapping of the cogwheel ontic states onto QM harmonic oscillators work.

However, also in the discrete case with N large, one has the strange situation that any probability distribution in φ which is peaked corresponds to a template state which, when expressed in the QFT basis states (2), has content also near N , i.e. at very large energy and very large number of particles. The author of this paper believes this necessitates a modification of the ontic states, which will be done in section 3.

2.3 Note on Background

Note also that one can express the QFT momentum basis states (2) as:

$$a^\dagger(\vec{k}_1) \dots a^\dagger(\vec{k}_n) |0\rangle = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_1 e^{+i\varphi_1 n_1} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_2 e^{+i\varphi_2 n_2} \dots |\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots\rangle_{\text{ont}} \quad (17)$$

With our choice that the absolute value squared of the coefficients in a template state is the probability to be in a certain ontic state $|\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots\rangle_{\text{ont}}$, this means that all QFT basis states are the same situation, since the absolute values squared of above coefficients are all 1. Clearly this cannot be correct. The author believes this also necessitates a modification of the ontic states, which will be discussed in section 3. We think that the complex coefficients are to be regarded w.r.t. some background, after which the momentum states are in fact different situations. Note for example that when adding two different momentum states the complex coefficients do become meaningful.

2.4 Crucial to Understand Interaction

A next big question is now how exactly typical quantum effects arise. E.g. how do we explain quantum interference? And how can we explain the quantum 2-slit experiment results? In the template states the basic math for this is already there: At any step in time we can write our template states as a superposition of any set of basis states. Taking the absolute value squared of the coefficients, for many choices of basis, will give interference effects. The big question is however why it is relevant at all to express our template state as a superposition of certain basis states. And why are the absolute values squared of the coefficients for these basis states related to a measured probability? It is exactly here that interactions become important. In QM the interactions happening when a measurement is performed bring the QM state into an eigenstate somehow belonging to the particular measurement being done. Understanding of the interaction in our ontic theories has to explain why the measurement brings the state into an eigenstate. And it has to explain why the coefficient of this eigenstate in the total template state is relevant for the measured probability. This is why it is crucial to understand interactions in our ontic theory.

For example, for a measurement of the charge observable, QFT says that after the measurement the system will be in an eigenstate of this observable, and the probabilities for each eigenstate are dictated by the coefficients of these eigenstates in the original superposition. Thus also from the ontological deterministic theory we have to explain why, just after the measurement, the system gets into an eigenstate of the observable. Also we have to explain why the probability for this is related to the coefficient of this eigenstate in the original superposition.

In other words, we have to explain why the eigenstates of observables, which are typically complex superpositions of the ontic states, are relevant for measurement outcomes. Clearly, because all measurements are interactions, here the interactions will become crucial. Therefore the most important next step in this research is to find how to include interactions in an ontological deterministic theory. Only when we know exactly what is happening at the ontological level during an interaction (needed for the measurement) we will be able to understand why the system evolves into one of the eigenstates during the measurement.

3 Adding Interaction in Ontic Theory

In the previous section we did a recap of the ontic theory behind free scalar QFT. We found that one can regard reality behind free scalar QFT as a set of cogwheels, one for each momentum value \vec{k}_i , each having a certain cogwheel position φ_i . These cogwheel positions satisfy a very simple deterministic evolution law (5). We now ask ourselves how interactions can be added in this ontic cogwheel theory.

One could suspect that for a scalar QFT with interaction, e.g. φ^4 -interaction, one has to start searching for ontic states in QFT all over again, similar to what was done for free scalar QFT in [3] & [4]. We might then find completely different variables parametrizing these new ontic states, and we might interpret these then as the reality behind scalar QFT with interaction. Clearly the whole Standard Model (SM) has a lot of interactions, and it would be a formidable task to eventually find a set of states that are ontological (in the sense as described in section 2) with *all* interactions of the SM present. The author believes it is a better strategy to first assume that the ontic theory behind a QFT with interaction is close to the ontic theory behind a free QFT. This is the strategy we will follow in this section and in this whole paper.

Thus how do we add interaction for our variables $\varphi(\vec{k})$, to the free evolution law (5)? Clearly this interaction has to be a local one, in order to satisfy relativistic requirements. Thus, before we can add interaction, we first need to translate our variables $\varphi(\vec{k})$ to \vec{x} -space, instead of \vec{k} -space. This is not so easy. Remember our variables have a range from 0 to 2π , so simply Fourier transforming $\varphi(\vec{k})$ will give awkward constraints for the variables in \vec{x} -space. The same holds for the Fourier transform of $e^{-i\varphi(\vec{k})}$, also here the corresponding variable in \vec{x} -space will satisfy awkward constraints. Clearly such constraints are easily violated by an evolution (with interaction), and it will be difficult to construct an evolution consistent with these constraints.

It seems here that the best thing we can do is add a degree of freedom $\rho(\vec{k})$ to our ontic theory,

$$\rho(\vec{k}) \in [0, \infty), \quad (18)$$

such that we can make a proper complex field

$$\varphi'(\vec{k}) \equiv \rho(\vec{k}) e^{-i\varphi(\vec{k})}. \quad (19)$$

From this complex field, which can take on values over the full complex plane, the Fourier transformed field $\varphi'(\vec{x})$ also ranges over the full complex field, without any constraints.

So which evolution do we assume for our new degree of freedom $\rho(\vec{k})$? A simple choice is to say

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt}(\vec{k}) = 0. \quad (20)$$

The observant reader will feel where this is going: If we now translate our total ontic variable $\varphi'(\vec{k})$ to \vec{x} -space, one will find that the field $\varphi(\vec{x})$ satisfies the classical free scalar field evolution. If we define

$$\varphi'(\vec{k}) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \varphi(\vec{k}) + \frac{1}{2} i \frac{1}{c\sqrt{\vec{k}^2 + \mu^2}} \dot{\varphi}(\vec{k}), \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(\vec{k}) &= \int d^3x \varphi(\vec{x}) e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{x}} \\ \dot{\varphi}(\vec{k}) &= \int d^3x \dot{\varphi}(\vec{x}) e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{x}}, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

with $\varphi(\vec{x})$ and $\dot{\varphi}(\vec{x})$ real scalar (classical) fields then these fields satisfy the Klein-Gordon evolution:

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial t^2}(\vec{x}, t) - \nabla^2 \varphi(\vec{x}, t) + \mu^2 \varphi(\vec{x}, t) = 0. \quad (23)$$

Having this relativistic evolution equation it is now straightforward to add interactions. For example we can add a φ^4 -interaction by changing the evolution to:

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial t^2}(\vec{x}, t) - \nabla^2 \varphi(\vec{x}, t) + \mu^2 \varphi(\vec{x}, t) = \lambda \varphi^3(\vec{x}, t) \quad (24)$$

Working out what the evolution of the template states in such an ontic theory with interaction is will be done below in section 5. We will see there that we get very close to scalar QFT with (self-)interaction in this way.

Note that in [4], (5.12) up to (5.15), expressions close to (23) & (42) were found. However there, because no extra field $\rho(\vec{k})$ was introduced, the evolution remained non-local.

What we thus have is an ontic theory with fundamental field variables $\varphi(\vec{x})$ and its time-derivative $\dot{\varphi}(\vec{x})$. Or, equivalently, fundamental field variables $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k})$.

We believe that the new variables $\rho(\vec{k})$ will help to explain the non-deterministic evolution of the (free QFT) ontic states, found below in section 4. We suspect that the ontic states from free QFT in fact contain uncertainty in $\rho(\vec{k})$, and this will explain their non-deterministic evolution. In this sense the ontic states found in free QFT are no longer true ontic states in the case of interaction.

Our current ontic theory has one more field variable $\rho(\vec{k})$ as a degree of freedom than the ontic theories found for scalar fields before in [3]. This we had to do to be able to add interactions in a local way, in \vec{x} -space.

We can also introduce ontic states in our ontic theory, to get closer to the formalism used in QFT:

$$|\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k})\rangle_{\text{ont}} \quad (25)$$

These states are normalized as follows.

$${}_{\text{ont}} \langle \rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k}) | \rho'(\vec{k}), \varphi'(\vec{k}) \rangle_{\text{ont}} = \prod_i \frac{1}{\rho_i} \delta(\rho_i - \rho'_i) \delta(\varphi_i - \varphi'_i) \quad (26)$$

These ontic states are situations where we know with certainty the values of $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k})$.

With these ontic states, as explained in [2], one can build template states

$$|\psi\rangle = \int_0^\infty d\rho_1 \rho_1 \int_0^\infty d\rho_2 \rho_2 \dots \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_1 \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_2 \dots c(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k})) |\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k})\rangle_{\text{ont}} \quad (27)$$

to form a whole Hilbert space. As in [2] we shall adhere to the convention that the probability density for the ontic variables ρ and φ to have certain values is

$$P(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k})) = \left| c(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k})) \right|^2. \quad (28)$$

In a very similar way as for the ontic theory with only the field variables $\varphi(\vec{k})$ we can now define the energy states:

$$|\rho(\vec{k}), n(\vec{k})\rangle \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\varphi_1 e^{+in_1 \varphi_1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\varphi_2 e^{+in_2 \varphi_2} \dots |\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k})\rangle_{\text{ont}} \quad (29)$$

(Here still we discretized momentum space on a lattice with spacing Δk and enumerated the vectors \vec{k} with a discrete index i .) These energy states are normalized as:

$$\langle \rho(\vec{k}), n(\vec{k}) | \rho'(\vec{k}), n'(\vec{k}) \rangle = \prod_i \frac{1}{\rho_i} \delta(\rho_i - \rho'_i) \delta_{n_i n'_i} \quad (30)$$

In terms of these energy states the free Hamiltonian is diagonal:

$$H_{\text{free}} = \int_0^\infty d\rho_1 \rho_1 \int_0^\infty d\rho_2 \rho_2 \dots \sum_{n_1=-\infty}^{+\infty} \sum_{n_2=-\infty}^{+\infty} \dots \sum_i \hbar c \sqrt{\vec{k}_i^2 + \mu^2} n_i |\rho(\vec{k}), n(\vec{k}) \rangle \langle \rho(\vec{k}), n(\vec{k})| \quad (31)$$

Of course this free Hamiltonian is heavily degenerate in $\rho(\vec{k})$.

The free evolution is now given by the Schrödinger equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} |\psi(t)\rangle = H_{\text{free}} |\psi(t)\rangle \quad (32)$$

We see that our new ontic theory is different from the one in section 2 and in [3] in two ways:

- We have an extra ontic field variable $\rho(\vec{k})$.
- We have a continuous ontic field variable $\varphi(\vec{k})$, for which the energy values $n(\vec{k})$ run from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$ instead of from 0 to $+\infty$.

This last point means our energy is not bounded from below, which is of course something to fix before we can reproduce QFT from our ontic theory.

With this ontic theory one doesn't have the problem mentioned at the end of section 2.2 anymore. Because our variables $n(\vec{k})$ run from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$ we can make peaked probability distributions for $\varphi(\vec{k})$ without requiring content at very large values of the $n(\vec{k})$. We still have the problem of mapping our states, where the n 's run from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$, onto the QFT states, where the n 's run from 0 to $+\infty$.

Also the problem discussed in section 2.3 might be solved. Depending on what the relation between the QFT basis states (2) and our states $|\rho(\vec{k}), n(\vec{k})\rangle$ in the ontic theory is, we might be able to introduce a background, using the new degrees of freedom $\rho(\vec{k})$. With this the momentum states will be situations with different probabilities.

If indeed the ontic theory behind any QFT is, at the basis, the corresponding classical theory, then this explains also why the construction of second quantization works so well. In this construction one always starts out with the classical field equation, promotes the coefficients of the energy eigenmodes to operators, for which one imposes certain (anti-)commutation relations. Then the introduction of the state space follows, and the basics of QFT are there. The author has always wondered why this construction of a new theory (QFT) by starting out from an old, classical theory works so well. Typically in physics, when new theories are introduced, one starts out from a completely new basis, which has nothing to do with the old theory anymore. Only in some limit does one recover the results of the old theory. But the basis is typically very different. If indeed the ontic theory behind a QFT is, at the basis, the corresponding classical field then the second quantization construction is more logical to understand.

3.1 Ontic Theory for Other QFTs

In the above section we conjectured that the ontic theory behind scalar QFT with interactions is a classical field theory with fields $\varphi(\vec{x})$ and $\dot{\varphi}(\vec{x})$, or equivalently with fields $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k})$. In this section we extend this conjecture to other QFTs occurring in the SM.

For all free QFTs one can always expand the field in terms of energy eigenmodes. For example, for Dirac QFT, one can write:

$$\psi(\vec{x}, t) \equiv \sum_{s=1}^2 \frac{1}{(2\pi\hbar)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d^3p \frac{mc^2}{E_p} (c_s(\vec{p}, t) u_s(\vec{p}) e^{+i\vec{p}\cdot\vec{x}/\hbar} + d_s^*(\vec{p}, t) v_s(\vec{p}) e^{-i\vec{p}\cdot\vec{x}/\hbar}) \quad (33)$$

The u 's and v 's are 4-spinors satisfying the following relations.

$$\begin{aligned} (\gamma^\mu p_\mu - mc) u_s(\vec{p}) &= 0 \\ (\gamma^\mu p_\mu + mc) v_s(\vec{p}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

We have the following orthogonality and normalization relations for the u 's and v 's.

$$\begin{aligned} u_r^\dagger(\vec{p}) u_s(\vec{p}) &= \frac{E_p}{mc^2} \delta_{rs} \\ v_r^\dagger(\vec{p}) v_s(\vec{p}) &= \frac{E_p}{mc^2} \delta_{rs} \\ u_r^\dagger(\vec{p}) v_s(-\vec{p}) &= 0 \\ v_r^\dagger(\vec{p}) u_s(-\vec{p}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Here E_p is defined as:

$$E_p \equiv \sqrt{c^2 \vec{p}^2 + m^2 c^4} \quad (36)$$

In the free case the coefficients c and d satisfy a simple evolution:

$$\begin{aligned} c_s(\vec{p}, t) &= c_s(\vec{p}) e^{-iE_p t/\hbar} \\ d_s(\vec{p}, t) &= d_s(\vec{p}) e^{-iE_p t/\hbar} \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

We can now write these coefficients c and d as:

$$\begin{aligned} c_s(\vec{p}) &\equiv \rho_s(\vec{p}) e^{-i\varphi_s(\vec{p})} \\ d_s(\vec{p}) &\equiv \rho'_s(\vec{p}) e^{-i\varphi'_s(\vec{p})} \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

Similar as in the scalar case our ontic variables are now ρ_s , φ_s , ρ'_s and φ'_s , only now we have in total 4 of them, i.s.o. 1.

Also for other QFTs, e.g. spin-1, a similar construction is possible, and we conjecture that the ontic variables are the ρ 's and the φ 's related to the classical spin-1 fields.

Note it is not clear yet how the above ontic variables and states for Dirac fermions are related to the ones found before in [2] (section 15) and summarized in [1].

4 Ontic Interaction Determined from QFT

Before we work out further the ontic theory with interaction, we will investigate in this section what the QFT evolution would mean for the evolution for the ontic states and the ontic variables found in section 2 and in [3].

From section 2 we know that in a free scalar QFT one can regard the ontic states as situations where one is certain about the value of the ontic variable $\varphi(\vec{k})$. Any other QFT state, which can be built out of these states, can be regarded as a situation where we are uncertain about the values of the ontic variable, with certain probabilities. One can now ask what would be the ontic states in a QFT with interaction. Take the example of φ^3 -interaction. One could think that the ontic states change drastically, and we would have to completely redo the analysis done to obtain the ontic states for the free case. This would then mean that, each time we add an interaction we would expect the ontic states to change drastically. Clearly the Standard Model contains a lot of different interactions, and before us lies the huge task to find the ontic states with all these interactions present. Alternatively one could also think that the ontic states with interaction present are the same as ones as in the free case. This is the line of inquiry we will follow in this paper.

In this section we will begin with the assumption that the ontic states in a QFT with interaction are the same as the ones for the corresponding free QFT, as advocated above. We will then determine what the QFT interaction means for the evolution of these ontic states. From this we then hope to read off a deterministic evolution for the ontic variables $\varphi(\vec{k})$, now including interaction.

We shall do this for the example of real scalar QFT with a φ^3 -interaction. (One might wonder why not φ^4 , because such a QFT has a stable vacuum, while the φ^3 one hasn't. For our purpose this latter property is less important now, for the purpose of making our point here the simplest non-trivial interaction serves best, and this is φ^3 .)

We can determine the effect of the interaction of QFT by first working out what is the effect of the operators a and a^\dagger on the ontic states. We found this in (13). The operator $a(\vec{k})$ works as follows on the ontic states:

$$a(\vec{k}_i) = \left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta k} \right)^{3/2} \left(c^2 \vec{k}^2 + c^2 \mu^2 \right)^{1/4} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi'_1 \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi'_2 \dots \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi_i \left(\sum_{k_i=0}^{\infty} \sqrt{k_i} e^{i+(k_i-1)\varphi_i - k_i\varphi'_i} \right) |\varphi'_1, \varphi'_2, \dots, \varphi'_{i-1}, \varphi_i, \varphi'_{i+1}, \dots\rangle_{\text{ont}} \langle \varphi'_1, \varphi'_2, \dots| \quad (39)$$

The operator a^\dagger works as the Hermitean conjugate of this.

Now the effect of the φ^3 -interaction, on any state in QFT, is given by the interaction Hamiltonian:

$$H_{\text{int}} = \lambda \int d^3x N(\varphi^3(\vec{x})) \quad (40)$$

$$\varphi(\vec{x}) = \frac{\sqrt{\hbar c}}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d^3k \frac{1}{c\sqrt{k^2 + \mu^2}} \left(a(\vec{k}) e^{+i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{x}} + a^\dagger(\vec{k}) e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{x}} \right) \quad (41)$$

From the above expressions we can see what the QFT φ^3 -interaction does to an ontic state. We see that the operator $a(\vec{k}_i)$, when operating on an ontic state, gives a superposition of ontic states, where the value of $\varphi_i = \varphi(\vec{k}_i)$ is changed by an amount $\Delta\varphi_i = \varphi'_i - \varphi_i$. Here all values of $\Delta\varphi_i$ contribute, because the sum over k_i in (13) gives non-zero for all $\Delta\varphi_i$.

Note this sum over k_i in (13) was extensively studied and worked out in [4]. Also there it was found that all $\Delta\varphi$ give non-zero.

With this we know that φ^3 -interaction makes an ontic state evolve into a superposition of ontic states, in which the values of $\varphi(\vec{k})$ have changed for 3 values of \vec{k} for each term in the superposition. Also this change $\Delta\varphi_i$ is not infinitesimal, i.e. the evolution works in a non-local way in $\varphi(\vec{k})$ -space. This means that, for the case of interaction, in our example φ^3 -interaction, the evolution found via QFT interaction is *not* deterministic for the ontic states.

Note that when one inserts above expression for a and a^\dagger (13) into the free Hamiltonian, then things combine exactly such as to get the free evolution of the ontic states, the contributions for non-zero $\Delta\varphi_i$ cancel out.

We believe that this non-deterministic, non-local (in $\varphi(\vec{k})$ -space), evolution for the ontic states hints at the existence of a hidden variable. We think that this is exactly the variable $\rho(\vec{k})$, introduced in the previous section.

This would mean that, with interaction, for none of the states in QFT state space we know the exact ontic state. For all QFT states, also the ones that are ontic in free QFT without interaction, there is some uncertainty regarding the ontic variables. And we think this uncertainty is in the $\rho(\vec{k})$ -variable.

5 Probability Evolution

In this section we return to the ontic theory with interaction from section 3 and show how the probability in such a classical scalar field theory *with* interaction evolves in time.

As interaction for our scalar field we shall choose φ^3 -interaction, because this is the most simple, non-trivial, interaction. One might wonder why not φ^4 , because such a QFT has a stable vacuum, while the φ^3 one hasn't. For our purpose this latter property is less important now, for the purpose of making our point here the simplest non-trivial interaction serves best, and this is φ^3 .

The (classical) evolution is:

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial t^2}(\vec{x}, t) - \nabla^2 \varphi(\vec{x}, t) + \mu^2 \varphi(\vec{x}, t) = \lambda \varphi^2(\vec{x}, t) \quad (42)$$

(Note that a φ^3 -interaction in the Hamiltonian gives a φ^2 -term in the equation of motion, as above.)

From this one can determine the evolution of the fields $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k})$, via (19), (21) & (22):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t}(\vec{k}, t) &= \frac{1}{4} \frac{\lambda c}{\sqrt{\vec{k}^2 + \mu^2}} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3 k' \left[i e^{+i\varphi(\vec{k}, t)} \right. \\ &\quad \left(\rho(\vec{k}', t) e^{-i\varphi(\vec{k}', t)} + \rho(-\vec{k}', t) e^{+i\varphi(-\vec{k}', t)} \right) \\ &\quad \left(\rho(\vec{k} - \vec{k}', t) e^{-i\varphi(\vec{k} - \vec{k}', t)} + \rho(-\vec{k} + \vec{k}', t) e^{+i\varphi(-\vec{k} + \vec{k}', t)} \right) + \\ &\quad \left. \text{c.c.} \right] \\ &\equiv g(\vec{k}, \rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k})) \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t}(\vec{k}, t) &= c\sqrt{\vec{k}^2 + \mu^2} + \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{4} \frac{\lambda c}{\sqrt{\vec{k}^2 + \mu^2}} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3 k' \left[\frac{1}{\rho(\vec{k}, t)} e^{+i\varphi(\vec{k}, t)} \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left(\rho(\vec{k}', t) e^{-i\varphi(\vec{k}', t)} + \rho(-\vec{k}', t) e^{+i\varphi(-\vec{k}', t)} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left(\rho(\vec{k} - \vec{k}', t) e^{-i\varphi(\vec{k} - \vec{k}', t)} + \rho(-\vec{k} + \vec{k}', t) e^{+i\varphi(-\vec{k} + \vec{k}', t)} \right) + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \text{c.c.} \right] \\
&\equiv c\sqrt{\vec{k}^2 + \mu^2} + h(\vec{k}, \rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k}))
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

Now define the probability to have certain values $\rho(\vec{k})$, $\varphi(\vec{k})$ for our ontic variables at time t as

$$P(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k}), t) \rho_1 d\rho_1 d\varphi_1 \rho_2 d\rho_2 d\varphi_2 \dots \tag{45}$$

Here we discretized again momentum space on a lattice with spacing Δk and enumerate the vectors \vec{k} with a discrete index i .

The volume element evolves in time as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho_1 d\rho_1 d\varphi_1 \rho_2 d\rho_2 d\varphi_2 \dots &\xrightarrow{dt} \rho'_1 d\rho'_1 d\varphi'_1 \rho'_2 d\rho'_2 d\varphi'_2 \dots = \\
&\rho_1 d\rho_1 d\varphi_1 \rho_2 d\rho_2 d\varphi_2 \dots \\
&\left[1 + dt \frac{g(\vec{k}_1)}{\rho(\vec{k}_1, t)} + dt \frac{g(\vec{k}_2)}{\rho(\vec{k}_2, t)} + \dots + \right. \\
&\quad dt \frac{\partial g(\vec{k}_1)}{\partial \rho(\vec{k}_1, t)} + dt \frac{\partial g(\vec{k}_2)}{\partial \rho(\vec{k}_2, t)} + \dots + \\
&\quad \left. dt \frac{\partial h(\vec{k}_1)}{\partial \varphi(\vec{k}_1, t)} + dt \frac{\partial h(\vec{k}_2)}{\partial \varphi(\vec{k}_2, t)} + \dots \right] + \\
&\mathcal{O}(dt^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{46}$$

Here we left out the arguments $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k})$ of g and h for the sake of clarity.

Now we can derive how the probability density P evolves in time by using the evolution of the fields $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k})$ (43) & (44):

$$\begin{aligned}
P(\rho(\vec{k}, t + dt), \varphi(\vec{k}, t + dt), t + dt) \rho'_1 d\rho'_1 d\varphi'_1 \rho'_2 d\rho'_2 d\varphi'_2 \dots &= \\
P(\rho(\vec{k}, t), \varphi(\vec{k}, t), t) \rho_1 d\rho_1 d\varphi_1 \rho_2 d\rho_2 d\varphi_2 \dots &
\end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

Expanding both sides in dt , up to order dt^1 , gives the desired evolution:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t}(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k}), t) = & - \sum_i \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho(\vec{k}_i)} \left(g(\vec{k}_i) P(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k}), t) \right) + \right. \\ & \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi(\vec{k}_i)} \left(h(\vec{k}_i) P(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k}), t) \right) + \\ & c\sqrt{\vec{k}_i^2 + \mu^2} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varphi(\vec{k}_i)}(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k}), t) + \\ & \left. \frac{g(\vec{k}_i)}{\rho(\vec{k}_i)} P(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k}), t) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

To cast our expressions more into the form they have in QFT we now define the probability density P to be an absolute value squared:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\rho(\vec{k}), \varphi(\vec{k}), t) = & \left| \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sum_{k_1=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sum_{k_2=-\infty}^{\infty} \dots e^{-ik_1 c\sqrt{\vec{k}_1^2 + \mu^2} t} e^{-ik_2 c\sqrt{\vec{k}_2^2 + \mu^2} t} \dots \right. \\ & \left. e^{+ik_1 \varphi(\vec{k}_1)} e^{+ik_2 \varphi(\vec{k}_2)} \dots d_{k_1, k_2, \dots}(\rho(\vec{k}), t) \right|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

By inserting this expression into (48) we can determine the evolution of d .

Clearly the maths has become quite complicated at this point, and to illustrate our points more clearly we will now move to the similar, but simpler, case of φ^1 -interaction. We believe that when we understand this simpler case of φ^1 we will also know how to handle φ^n .

6 Probability Evolution for φ^1 -Interaction

The above calculation for φ^3 -interaction in the ontic theory is quite complicated. To simplify things a bit we can first look at φ^1 -interaction. This is not a real interaction of course, but the maths will be very similar to the φ^3 case, but much simpler. This case will suffice to make our point that we can reproduce QFT interactions from a classical ontic theory. We believe that the same reasoning as below, for φ^1 , can be applied for the φ^n -case.

The evolution for the case of φ^1 -interaction is:

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial t^2}(\vec{x}, t) - \nabla^2 \varphi(\vec{x}, t) + \mu^2 \varphi(\vec{x}, t) = \lambda \quad (50)$$

In this case only the fields $\rho(\vec{k} = \vec{0})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k} = \vec{0})$ have a non-free evolution, which can be determined from (19), (21) & (22), and is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t}(t) &= \frac{1}{4} i \frac{\lambda c}{\mu} \frac{(2\pi)^3}{\Delta k^3} (e^{+i\varphi(t)} - e^{-i\varphi(t)}) \\ &\equiv g(\varphi) \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t}(t) &= c\mu - \frac{1}{4} \frac{\lambda c}{\mu} \frac{(2\pi)^3}{\Delta k^3} \frac{1}{\rho(t)} (e^{+i\varphi(t)} + e^{-i\varphi(t)}) \\ &\equiv c\mu + h(\rho, \varphi) \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

Here

$$\begin{aligned}\rho(t) &\equiv \rho(\vec{k} = \vec{0}, t) \\ \varphi(t) &\equiv \varphi(\vec{k} = \vec{0}, t).\end{aligned}\tag{53}$$

From here onward we will leave out the free, and therefore uninteresting, evolution of the momentum modes other than $\vec{k} = \vec{0}$.

The evolution of the probability density in ρ and φ can be derived in the same way as in section 5, and is now:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial P}{\partial t}(\rho, \varphi, t) &= -g(\varphi) \frac{\partial P}{\partial \rho}(\rho, \varphi, t) - h(\rho, \varphi) \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varphi}(\rho, \varphi, t) - c\mu \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varphi}(\rho, \varphi, t) + \\ &\quad - \frac{g(\varphi)}{\rho} P(\rho, \varphi, t) - \frac{\partial h}{\partial \varphi}(\rho, \varphi) P(\rho, \varphi, t)\end{aligned}\tag{54}$$

To cast our expressions in a form closer to QFT we want the probability to be an absolute value squared. Therefore we introduce $d_k(\rho)$ as follows. Together with this introduction of the absolute values squared we also introduce energy modes to describe the probability in φ .

$$P(\rho, \varphi, t) = \left| \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-ikc\mu t} e^{+ik\varphi} d_k(\rho, t) \right|^2\tag{55}$$

The normalization of d_k is:

$$\int_0^{\infty} d\rho \rho \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi P(\rho, \varphi, t) = 1 = \int_0^{\infty} d\rho \rho \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} |d_k(\rho, t)|^2\tag{56}$$

Then the evolution of d is:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial d_k}{\partial t}(\rho, t) &= \frac{1}{4} i \frac{\lambda c}{\mu} \frac{(2\pi)^3}{\Delta k^3} \left[\left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} + \frac{k-1}{\rho} \right) d_{k-1}(\rho, t) e^{+ic\mu t} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left(+\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} + \frac{k+1}{\rho} \right) d_{k+1}(\rho, t) e^{-ic\mu t} \right]\end{aligned}\tag{57}$$

This evolution can be determined by inserting (55) into (54). Note that there is some freedom of choice here, because our $d_k(\rho)$ has more degrees of freedom than the $P(\rho, \varphi)$. Any choice here is correct of course.

Now define states $|\psi(t)\rangle$ as follows.

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = \int_0^{\infty} d\rho \rho \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-ikc\mu t} d_k(\rho, t) |\rho, k\rangle\tag{58}$$

These states are normalized:

$$\langle \psi(t) | \psi(t) \rangle = \int_0^{\infty} d\rho \rho \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} |d_k(\rho, t)|^2 = 1\tag{59}$$

The evolution of this state is now:

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi(t+dt)\rangle &= |\psi(t)\rangle + \int_0^\infty d\rho \rho \sum_{k=-\infty}^\infty e^{-ikc\mu t} d_k(\rho, t) \left[-ikc\mu dt |\rho, k\rangle + \right. \\
&\quad dt \frac{1}{4} i \frac{\lambda c}{\mu} \frac{(2\pi)^3}{\Delta k^3} \left(\left(+\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} + \frac{k+1}{\rho} \right) |\rho, k+1\rangle + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. \left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} + \frac{k-1}{\rho} \right) |\rho, k-1\rangle \right) \right] + \\
&\quad \mathcal{O}(dt^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

From this we can determine how the states $|\rho, k\rangle$ evolve in time:

$$\begin{aligned}
|\rho, k\rangle &\xrightarrow{dt} |\rho, k\rangle - ikc\mu dt |\rho, k\rangle + \\
&\quad dt \frac{1}{4} i \frac{\lambda c}{\mu} \frac{(2\pi)^3}{\Delta k^3} \left[\left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} + \frac{k-1}{\rho} \right) |\rho, k-1\rangle + \left(+\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} + \frac{k+1}{\rho} \right) |\rho, k+1\rangle \right] + \\
&\quad \mathcal{O}(dt^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

This is beginning to look like the evolution we get from QFT, for the basis states (2). If we normalize these QFT basis states to 1, as follows,

$$|n\rangle \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{n!}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\Delta k^3}{c\mu(2\pi)^3}} \right)^n \left(a^\dagger(\vec{0}) \right)^n |0\rangle, \tag{62}$$

then the evolution in a QFT with φ^1 -interaction is:

$$\begin{aligned}
|n\rangle &\xrightarrow{dt} |n\rangle - idt\mu c n |n\rangle + \\
&\quad -idt \frac{\lambda c^{3/2}}{\sqrt{2\mu\hbar^{3/2}}} \sqrt{\frac{(2\pi)^3}{(\Delta k)^3}} \sqrt{n} |n-1\rangle - idt \frac{\lambda c^{3/2}}{\sqrt{2\mu\hbar^{3/2}}} \sqrt{\frac{(2\pi)^3}{(\Delta k)^3}} \sqrt{n+1} |n+1\rangle + \\
&\quad \mathcal{O}(dt^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

Here the QFT Hamiltonian (in the Schrödinger picture) is:

$$H = \int_{-\infty}^\infty d^3x \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{c} \dot{\varphi}(\vec{x}) \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\vec{\nabla} \varphi(\vec{x}) \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu^2 \varphi(\vec{x})^2 + \lambda \varphi(\vec{x}) \right) \tag{64}$$

The φ -operator field is given by:

$$\varphi(\vec{x}, t) = \frac{\sqrt{\hbar}}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{-\infty}^\infty d^3k \frac{1}{\sqrt{k^2 + \mu^2}} \left(a(\vec{k}) e^{-ik \cdot x} + a^\dagger(\vec{k}) e^{+ik \cdot x} \right) \tag{65}$$

Now compare the evolution from our ontic theory (61) to the evolution from QFT (63). Our ontic evolution looks a lot like the one from QFT, we recognize the kinetic term, and the interaction terms where n or k is raised or lowered by 1. In our ontic evolution we still have the ρ , not present in the QFT evolution.

We can make the similarity even larger by considering specific states in our space of states $|\rho, k\rangle$. Consider the following states:

$$|n\rangle' = \sqrt{\frac{n\Delta}{\delta(\rho=0)}} |\rho = n\Delta, n\rangle \quad (66)$$

These states are also normalized to 1. Δ Is some quantity in units of ρ . We shall take this quantity Δ to be small.

Using (61), these states evolve in time as:

$$\begin{aligned} |n\rangle' \xrightarrow{dt} & |n\rangle' - idtc\mu n |n\rangle' + \\ & idt \frac{1}{4} \frac{\lambda c}{\mu} \frac{(2\pi)^3}{\Delta k^3} \frac{1}{\Delta} \left[\frac{\sqrt{n-1}}{\sqrt{n}} |n-1\rangle' + \frac{\sqrt{n+1}}{\sqrt{n}} |n+1\rangle' \right] + \\ & \mathcal{O}(\Delta^1) + \mathcal{O}(dt^2) \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

This evolution is very similar to the QFT evolution (63). The only thing wrong is the factors in n in front of the states $|n \pm 1\rangle'$.

This is a very important result: From a purely classical field theory, considering specific sets of states, we can get a probability evolution which is almost identical to the QFT state evolution. We believe that, by tuning the states (66) further we can exactly reproduce the QFT evolution.

Also the calculation of the final probability in ρ is the same as in QFT, including the Born rule. The probability density to measure a value ρ is:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\rho, t) &= \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi P(\rho, \varphi, t) = \\ & \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} |d_k(\rho, t)|^2 = \\ & \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} |\langle \rho, k | \psi(t) \rangle|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

If our state $|\psi(t)\rangle$ is always built up only from the states $|n\rangle'$,

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n(t) |n\rangle', \quad (69)$$

then this is:

$$P(\rho, t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} \left| \langle \rho, k | \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n(t) \sqrt{\frac{n\Delta}{\delta(0)}} |\rho = n\Delta, n\rangle \right|^2 \quad (70)$$

For the case of our states $|n\rangle'$ ρ can only take on the values $n\Delta$. The probability to have one of these discrete values for ρ is:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\rho = n\Delta, t) &= \int_{n\Delta-\varepsilon}^{n\Delta+\varepsilon} d\rho \rho P(\rho, t) = \\ & |c_n(t)|^2 = \\ & |\langle n | \psi(t) \rangle|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

Thus we find that also in our ontic theory the probability to measure a value $\rho = n\Delta$ is given by the same formula as in QFT, for the case we limit the state space to the states $|n\rangle'$.

The similarity to QFT can also be demonstrated directly from $d_k(\rho, t)$, not going to the states first. To show this choose specific shapes for $d_k(\rho, t)$ as follows:

$$d_k(\rho, t) = c_k(t) \frac{1}{\sqrt{k\Delta\delta(\rho = 0)}} \delta(\rho - k\Delta) e^{+ikc\mu t} \quad (72)$$

Here $k \geq 0$.

By inserting this into the evolution of $d_k(\rho, t)$ (57) one can show that the c 's evolve as follows.

$$\frac{\partial c_k}{\partial t}(t) = -ikc\mu c_k(t) + \frac{1}{4} i \frac{\lambda c}{\mu} \frac{(2\pi)^3}{\Delta k^3} \frac{1}{\Delta} \left[\frac{\sqrt{k}}{\sqrt{k-1}} c_{k-1}(t) + \frac{\sqrt{k}}{\sqrt{k+1}} c_{k+1}(t) \right] + \mathcal{O}(\Delta) \quad (73)$$

The QFT evolution of similar coefficients c can be read of from (63), and is:

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n(t) |n\rangle \quad (74)$$

$$\frac{\partial c_n}{\partial t}(t) = -ic\mu n c_n(t) - i \frac{\lambda c^{3/2}}{\sqrt{2\mu\hbar^{3/2}}} \sqrt{\frac{(2\pi)^3}{\Delta k^3}} \left[\sqrt{n} c_{n-1}(t) + \sqrt{n+1} c_{n+1}(t) \right] \quad (75)$$

Also here we observe a clear similarity between (73) and (75).

6.1 Notes

Above we have demonstrated the similarity between the evolution from our ontic theory and QFT. For this we had to assume that the quantity Δ is small. Also, as the observant reader might have noticed, there is a problem at $n = 0$, for our states (66). There the ontic evolution takes a state with $n = 0$ over into an ontic state $|\rho, k = -1\rangle$. Thus our states (66) are only proper solutions, going over in themselves under evolution, if we stay away from $n = 0$, thus if we stay away from small ρ . As long as we begin with a probability density that has content only far enough away from $\rho = 0$ then our states (66) are a good solution.

In the end we are also interested in states like (66) that correspond to QFT for small n . This because these QFT states refer to few-particle states, and we want to understand, from an ontological theory, how these few-particle states behave. This means we have to find states like (66) that evolve as in QFT, up to and including order Δ^1 , or more accurate. Hopefully then we also find that these states don't go over into states for $k < 0$. We believe that we can tune the states (66) further to be good solutions also for small n .

7 Discussion

Let's summarize what we did in the above. We started out from the ontic theory known from free scalar QFT, where the underlying reality is a set of cogwheels with position φ , one for each momentum value \vec{k} . All these cogwheel positions $\varphi(\vec{k})$ follow a simple evolution law. To include interactions in this theory, in a local and relativistic manner, we added the degree of freedom $\rho(\vec{k})$ to the ontic theory. With this the ontic theory, which we believe underlies scalar QFT, becomes the corresponding classical scalar field theory.

For this classical scalar field theory we determined the evolution of the fields $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k})$, including interaction. We determined the probability density evolution for these ontic fields. To describe this probability we introduced a formalism where the probability is the absolute value squared of a complex quantity $d_k(\rho, t)$, as in QFT. Here we also introduced energy states $k(\vec{k})$ to describe the probability in $\varphi(\vec{k})$. We determined the evolution of this $d_k(\rho, t)$. We also introduced corresponding states, and determined their evolution. This evolution, because we formulated everything in terms of the degrees of freedom $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $k(\vec{k})$, looks already a lot like QFT. This wouldn't have been the case if we formulated the probability evolution in terms of e.g. the ontic fields $\varphi(\vec{x})$ and $\dot{\varphi}(\vec{x})$.

Having found the evolution of the states we focussed on a special limited set of states. We found that these states evolve into each other under the evolution in the ontic theory. Additionally we saw that the evolution of these states is very similar to the QFT evolution. All of this we demonstrated for the case of φ^1 -interaction, but we think it will also hold for the more complicated case of φ^n -interaction.

By tuning our special states further we think we can exactly reproduce QFT evolution, for our set of special states.

This is a very important, but surprising result. Apparently, from a purely classical and deterministic theory, by selecting a certain set of states from the total state space, we can reproduce QFT. Of course we still have to explain why then only this limited set of states occurs in reality and in QFT. For this we might need some special ingredient, like e.g. the fast variables proposed in [10]. But to reproduce QFT evolution a classical evolution together with the selection of a limited part of state space is enough.

Having obtained this important result, there are a number of big open questions still:

- As mentioned already: Why do not all states $|\rho, \varphi\rangle$ occur in QFT, but only the states $|n\rangle'$ (66)?

This is related to the uncertainty principle. If we can explain why only our limited set of states occur in reality, then we can also explain the uncertainty principle, and why $\varphi(\vec{x})$ and $\dot{\varphi}(\vec{x})$, or equivalently $c(\vec{k})$ and $c^*(\vec{k})$, are not both simultaneously measurable with 100% accuracy.

On how to explain this we are still uncertain. It might be connected to the fast hidden variables, as proposed in [10], [11] & [12]. If these fast variables somehow introduce a spontaneous element into the interaction we might be able to explain why certain measurements are impossible with 100% accuracy. These fast variables would then be our variables $\rho(\vec{k})$ and $\varphi(\vec{k})$ for very large \vec{k} .

- How will we reproduce the exactly correct factors in n in our ontic evolution (67)?

We think that we can tune the states $|n\rangle'$ further, to obtain a set of states that also evolves into itself under the ontic evolution for small values of n , and that has

the same factors in n in this evolution as in QFT. For this new set of states the evolution has to agree with QFT up to and including order Δ^1 . Also it has to be such that the ontic evolution doesn't take the state with $n = 0$ to an ontic state with $k = -1$.

- Where do the infinities known from QFT arise in our ontic theory approach?

All our probability evolutions in the ontic theory will give finite results. At some point an approximation or something must come in, after which we reproduce the infinities known in QFT. Perhaps this is connected to the further tuning of our states (66). Maybe in this tuning some approximation is done with which we can understand that divergences arise. This will also give insight in why these infinities can be absorbed in the QFT coupling constants, which is a deep mystery in QFT.

- Why is our energy not bounded from below?

The free Hamiltonian found in our ontic theory behind scalar QFT (31) doesn't have a lower bound. When we find the answer to the first question above, and are able to avoid that the ontic evolution takes our special states $|n\rangle'$ to values of n below 0, then we have also managed to get a lower bound for the energy.

8 Continuous vs. Discrete

In the above we investigate classical field theories as the ontic theories behind QFTs. In the literature so far one typically proposes discrete ontic theories. See e.g. [2] & [9].

The author of this paper does believe that physics, at the most fundamental level, has a discrete, i.s.o. a continuous, structure. We believe that the continuum is an invention of mankind which works well on a macroscopic level. The continuum limit also helps a lot to make the equations governing many physical processes solvable. Typically differential equations are easier to solve than difference equations. Why then do we propose continuous theories as the ontic theories behind QFT?

We think it is currently too early to be able to guess what the discrete structure of reality is like. Take the example of the search for a discrete theory of spacetime, like for example the dynamical triangulations (DT) or causal dynamical triangulations (CDT) approach. After tens of years of research it has appeared very difficult to come up with a discrete spacetime structure that matches our continuous spacetime in a certain macroscopic limit. See e.g. [5], [6], [7], [8] & [9]. Reproducing relativity is also very difficult in a discrete spacetime. This demonstrates that currently we have too few hints to guess the discrete structure behind spacetime. It is like trying to find Quantum Mechanics, from only the condition that the classical limit of this new theory reproduces classical mechanics. This is clearly impossible. QM was found by having actual experimental hints of the structure behind classical mechanics. Only when the experimental data piled up theorists were able to formulate the new Quantum theory.

In order to find a discrete theory we would need the same, we would need experimental data showing some effects of the discrete structure. Clearly at this point in time, where all observations we know are in complete accordance with the (continuous) SM, we are not at that stage yet. This is why the author claims it is too early to search for discrete (ontological) theories.

For this reason we think it is most fruitful to currently search for *continuous* ontological theories.

Another reason to start with continuous ontic theories is to avoid having to solve multiple problems at once. It is already difficult enough to find an ontological theory behind QFT, let alone at the same time figure out what is the discrete structure of reality.

Summarizing, the author of this paper also believes that nature, at the deepest level, is discrete, and can be described by a cellular automaton, but we also believe that discovering how exactly this cellular automaton looks like is not feasible now, given the lack of experimental hints about this discrete nature.

Appendix: The Born Rule

In the above we mentioned that, in template states, we choose the coefficients c (in front of the ontic states) to be related to the probability P to be in this ontic state as

$$P = |c|^2. \quad (76)$$

In this section we will give an argument why this is very convenient.

Let's say that our QM system is described by ontic states $|n\rangle$. Typically a measurement of a certain variable y will bring the system into a state

$$\sum_n c_{n,y} |n\rangle. \quad (77)$$

Let's say the measurement is complete, i.e. by doing the measurement we determine the complete QM state the system is in.

Now it is very convenient if we can write the state before the measurement as a superposition of the states after measurement (77). This means we want to be able to write any state

$$\sum_n c'_n |n\rangle \quad (78)$$

as

$$\sum_n c'_n |n\rangle = \sum_y c_y \sum_n c_{n,y} |n\rangle. \quad (79)$$

This is possible if we can find c_y such that

$$c'_n = \sum_y c_y c_{n,y}. \quad (80)$$

Now if we would have chosen the coefficients c as being directly the probabilities P , i.e. $P = c$, then the above relation means we want to be able to find, for any P'_n , P_y such that

$$P'_n = \sum_y P_y P_{n,y}, \quad (81)$$

where $P_{n,y}$ is fixed for a certain measurement.

Clearly this is not possible for P 's that are real, semi-positive-definite quantities. It is possible if we choose the coefficients as real numbers without any constraints, or if we chose them as complex numbers. If the $c_{n,y}$ are independent, which is expected for a measurement, then the inverse exists and we can find c_y from (80).

If we choose the probability as (76) and if we also choose the $c_{n,y}$ orthogonal then normalization is also convenient:

$$\sum_n |c'_n|^2 = \sum_y \sum_{y'} \sum_n c_y c_{y'}^* c_{n,y} c_{n,y'}^* = \sum_y \sum_{y'} c_y c_{y'}^* \delta_{yy'} = \sum_y |c_y|^2 \quad (82)$$

Here one can also see that any other relation of probabilities to coefficients, like e.g. $P = |c|^3$ would not have been very convenient.

The above, to the author's knowledge, is the main motivation for the choice (76).

Acknowledgements

The author wishes to thank G. 't Hooft for answering questions on the meaning of energy states and the related background to make them different. (This is discussed in section 2.3.)

The author also wishes to thank R. Schouenberg and R. van Kessel for valuable motivational conversations and for encouragements to publish results.

References

- [1] M. van Kessel, ‘Ontological States in Non-Interacting Quantum Field Theories’, arXiv:2407.13799 [quant-ph]
- [2] G. 't Hooft, ‘The Cellular Automaton Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics’, *Fundamental Theories of Physics*, Vol. 185, Springer International Publishing, 2016, arXiv:1405.1548v3 [quant-ph]
- [3] G. 't Hooft, ‘An ontological description for relativistic, massive bosons.’, arXiv:2306.09885v1 [quant-ph]
- [4] G. 't Hooft, ‘The Hidden Ontological Variable in Quantum Harmonic Oscillators’, arXiv:2407.18153v4 [quant-ph]
- [5] A. Ilachinski, ‘Cellular Automata, A Discrete Universe’, World Scientific (2001)
- [6] A. Hagar, ‘Discrete or Continuous?’, Cambridge University Press (2014)
- [7] J. Ambjørn, M. Carfora, A. Marzuoli, ‘The Geometry of Dynamical Triangulations’, Springer (1997)
- [8] R. Loll, ‘Quantum Gravity from Causal Dynamical Triangulations: A Review’, arXiv:1905.08669v1 [hep-th]
- [9] S. Wolfram, ‘A New Kind of Science’, Wolfram Media Inc. (2002)
- [10] G. 't Hooft, ‘Fast Vacuum Fluctuations and the Emergence of Quantum Mechanics’, *Found Phys* 51, 63 (2021), arXiv:2010.02019 [quant-ph]
- [11] G. 't Hooft, ‘Explicit construction of Local Hidden Variables for any quantum theory up to any desired accuracy’, arXiv:2103.04335 [quant-ph]
- [12] G. 't Hooft, ‘Quantum Foundations as a Guide for Refining Particle Theories’, arXiv:2312.09396v1 [hep-th]
- [13] C. Wetterich, ‘Probabilistic cellular automata for interacting fermionic quantum field theories’, *Nuclear Physics B* 963115296 (2021), arXiv:2007.06366 [quant-ph]